

A NOTE ON THE ACTION OF STRONG SOLUTIONS OF POTASSIUM FERRICYANIDE.

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An alkaline solution of $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ is a well known oxidising agent, but it does not appear to have been recorded that if the alkali is sufficiently strong, free oxygen is obtained.

On adding 50 c.c. of aqueous KOH solution (1:1) to 5 g. of $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ in 10 c.c. of water, the $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ is mostly thrown out of solution as an orange-red precipitate, which floats owing to the gas disengaged on its surface. At room temperature (30°), the reaction is slow but is almost complete after being left overnight. The gas evolved contains about 93.5% of oxygen, the rest being nitrogen. On heating to 100° the effervescence becomes fairly brisk, the reaction being complete in about an hour; the gas contains approximately 95% of oxygen. The maximum volume of gas obtained from 5 g. of $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ was 79.5 c.c. at N.T.P. There remains after the reaction a pale yellow liquid with a cream-coloured crystalline precipitate. The precipitate consists of slender prisms which do not lose weight appreciably on heating to 100° . It dissolves in water giving a clear solution showing the reactions of a ferrocyanide, and which, on concentration, deposits the characteristic tablet-shaped crystals of $K_4Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 3H_2O$. The precipitate appears, therefore, to be anhydrous $K_4Fe(CN)_6$. The alkaline solution from the reaction contains a little $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ but no $K_4Fe(CN)_6$. These results suggest that the main reaction may be represented by the following equation,

With saturated KOH solution the reaction is slower, probably owing to the greater insolubility of $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ in this solution. With equal volumes of the $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ and KOH solutions, oxygen is evolved, but after long heating the solution remains brown. When the volume of KOH is reduced to one-fifth the volume of the $K_3Fe(CN)_6$, there is no noticeable evolution of gas in the cold, and only slight effervescence on heating. With 50 c.c. of NaOH solution (1 NaOH : 1.5 water) and 5 g. of $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ in 10 c.c. of water, the $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ is precipitated but very slight

effervescence takes place in the cold ; at 100° a slow evolution of gas containing 97-98% oxygen occurs. The resulting cream-coloured precipitate consists of hexagonal plates.

That the volume of oxygen obtained is appreciably less than the theoretical amount, 85 c.c., and the presence of some nitrogen in the gas, suggest that a secondary reaction occurs in which some (CN) groups are oxidised. But as no $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ is formed when the alkali is strong, it appears that no $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]'''$ radicals are completely broken up.

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